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BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE

Biology and medicinal properties of field species

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Abstract. Despite the long history of medicinal plant collection in Uzbekistan, there is a lack of information on the current state of the natural population of even the most promising medicinal, food, technical and other raw material plants. there is. The analysis of available materials showed the need to organize a wide scientific research program to clarify the current state of natural medicinal plant reserves, to study the rate of population recovery (results) after harvesting raw materials.

Basic words. Flower, vegetation, budding, gross flowering, fruit, raw material, actinomorph, five-membered calyx, gultoji, gultoji leaves, pollinator, area.

Enter. At present, medicinal plants are grown in specialized farms of our country, farmers, foresters, peasants and other types of ownership. However, due to the fact that the technologies of their cultivation and cultivation are not perfectly developed, some problems are being created that need to be solved and developed. Therefore, providing the pharmaceutical industry with high-quality, abundant, low-cost and environmentally friendly raw materials remains one of the urgent tasks.

Research object and methods used We used the methods of Karshibayev and Ponomoryov to study plant biology, the biology of plant growth, development, and flowering.

The result and their analysis. The genus *Hypericum* belongs to the Hypericaceae family. This family includes 47 families and about 950 species. Most of the species of this family are widespread on the earth, their main representatives are trees and shrubs, distributed in tropical climates. A minority are herbaceous plants, and this group also includes the genus *Hupericum*. This category includes 200 to 400 species. There are 51 species of this family in the territory of the

Commonwealth of Nations. In the territory of the Russian Federation, there are three species of this family (*H. hirsutum* L., *H. perforatum* L. and *H. maculatum* Crantz.) and six species in Central Asia (*H. hirsutum* L., *H. perforatum* L., *H. gebleri* L., *H. scabrum* L., *H. elongatum* L., *H. helianthemoids* L.) are found.

The root system of *H. perforatum* is strongly developed. In the underground part, there are many rhizomes, their length is up to 3-15 cm, and their width is up to 3-5 mm, often they penetrate 2-5 cm, sometimes up to 10 cm in soft soils. Up to 3-4 above-ground parts - stems grow from large root stems. A large number of pubic roots are formed on the root stem. In addition to them, more strongly developed arrow roots are formed, which reach a depth of 155-160 cm in the soil.

Three species of the *Hupericum* family are found in Uzbekistan:

H. elongatum Lyedieb. - long field; *N. scabrum* L. - red scab; *N. perforatum* L. - a hole chayot, field.

***H. elongatum* Lyedyeb.** - A long field. Perennial herb. The height is 40-50 cm, the leaves are opposite, 15-20 mm. Changchili is short compared to the petals, it blooms and seeds in July-August. It grows in rocky and soft soils in the mountain zone. The flowers are collected in a shield-shaped or round-egg-shaped inflorescence. Petals are 18-20 mm, longer than pollen. The long field flower blooms in May and June, and bears fruit in July and August. The fruit is an elongated pod.

***H. scabrum* L.** - Perennial herb. Height 20 - 40 cm. The stem and branches are gnarled. The leaves are long - pencil or lanceolate, 10-15 mm. Branches grow from leaf axils. The ball-flowered thyroid flower blooms and seeds in May - July. It grows in rocky and gravelly areas of hills and mountains. It is found in Central Asia, North Africa, Iran, Mongolia, Japan, China and North America.

In Uzbekistan, it grows in the foothills of Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Samarkand, Jizzakh, along streams, in gardens.

***H. perforatum* L.** – A field with holey leaves. This plant naturally can be obtained from 15-20 quintals of dried raw material per hectare in some mountain regions.

H. perforatum is a southern boreal Eurasian species in the Commonwealth of Independent States, and it is quite widespread on Earth. *H. perforatum* is found

in the middle part of Europe, Central and Asia Minor, North Africa, Iran, Mongolia, Japan, China and North America. *H. perforatum* is often widespread in dry, bright areas, it can be found in mountainous areas up to 2300 m, as well as in forest-steppe and forest regions. Its growth area in nature is very small, and it often occupies small areas.

H. perforatum It is a perennial herb, its height reaches 30-100 cm. The stem grows upright, the upper part is branched, cylindrical in shape. The leaves are opposite to each other on the stem, oval and elliptic in shape, on a branchless stem. The leaves have a small amount of shiny black glandular hairs. The flower organs are free actinomorphic, the calyx is five-membered, the corolla is five, the corolla leaves are light yellow in color, there are many pollinators, often their number is up to 50-60 pieces. Based on pollinators, they are united in three sets. The node is egg-shaped and its length reaches 3-5 mm. A large number of flowers are combined into a tuberos inflorescence. The fruit is an elongated ovoid capsule, 6 mm long and 5 mm wide. A large number of seeds are placed in a very small fruit.

In scientific medicine, the flower is used to remove stomach worms, to prevent fever (malaria) and diarrhea. In folk medicine, this plant is used to treat stomach worms and various worms in the stomach.

Medicinal preparations of the field plant (infusion, nastoyka, liquid extract, imanin preparation) in Kyzylpoycha scientific medicine are used for gastrointestinal (colitis, diarrhea), oral cavity (gingivitis, stomatitis) and II and III diseases. used in the treatment of degree burns. In folk medicine, ground organs are used in the treatment of jaundice (decoction).

Conclusion

To sum up, field species in our climate, only one type of open-leaved field is cultivated, the area of the other two species has decreased. Today, we are carrying out scientific research works for the culturalization of the distribution area and biology of these two species.

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HISTORICAL SCIENCE

Development of industrial capacity of Khorazm region: reforms and results

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Annotation: This article discusses the attraction of foreign investments to the economy of Khorezm region, reforms in the economic sphere.

Keywords: investment, industry, Khorezm region, export, joint venture, economy.

If we look at the international recognition of reforms in Uzbekistan, which is being renewed rapidly, in the past historically short period, the political position and influence of Uzbekistan in the Central Asian region and the world has increased dramatically. In the world, the spirit of confidence in New Uzbekistan and the principles of striving for cooperation with the country have increased.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, from the first days of the state administration, in the implementation of the country's foreign policy, set the strengthening of friendly relations and mutually beneficial cooperation with all countries, first of all, with neighboring countries, as a first-level task, and took measures to attract foreign investments and investments to the economy of the country. As a result, during the first five years of the development of New Uzbekistan, a number of activities were carried out to liberalize foreign economic activities and support exports. In particular, the approach to relations with partner countries and international financial institutions has changed radically. Artificial barriers to foreign trade activities were removed, and the export procedure was introduced without advance payments and without guarantee obligations. Also, at a completely new stage of Uzbekistan's development -

On the basis of the priorities defined in the Action Strategy, a new economic policy has been consistently implemented, which is to rapidly develop the industry by attracting foreign investments, which is an important factor for the rapid development of the country, and to expand the share of the industry in the gross domestic product.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoev, on November 11, 2016, at the pre-election meeting held in the Shavot district, outlined specific plans for the modernization of the economy of the Khorezm region as well as for the further development of agriculture, textiles, medicine, tourism, art and other areas. Practical work on the implementation of these issues was started in the region, and significant positive changes were achieved in a short period of time. Investment funds totaling 1 trillion 600 billion soums were attracted to all sectors of the region for two years from all sources.

Indeed, at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the adoption of the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" initiated the period of fundamental democratic reforms and transformational changes in Uzbekistan. In 2017 itself, 11 programs for the development of the republic's territories, as well as 36 programs for the development of individual districts and cities, were adopted.

During the implementation of priority tasks set by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan during his visits to the region in 2017, 2018, the investment attractiveness of the region and the inflow of foreign investment accelerated. In particular, in 2018, the delegation of the Khorezm region visited Belarus, China, Turkey, Turkmenistan and the Russian Federation in order to attract foreign direct investment and develop trade and economic relations. As a result, agreements on the implementation of investment projects with a total value of 181 million US dollars, export contracts worth 62 million US dollars were signed.

Also, it was agreed with the United Arab Emirates company "Armada Group" to attract investments of 100 million dollars to build a tourist complex around "Govukkol", and with the Saudi Arabian company "Ajlan and Bros Holding" on the organization of textile clusters and the implementation of hotel projects. achievement served to further develop the investment potential of the region.

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MEDICAL SCIENCE

The role of regulatory cytokines in gastrointestinal forms of food allergies in children

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Annotation: Allergic diseases currently occupy a leading place among the most common chronic pathology in childhood. Food allergy is considered today as a multifactorial pathology, in the occurrence and development of which a number of both genetic and environmental factors play a role.

The increase in the prevalence, severity of clinical manifestations of food allergy, the possibility of forming oral tolerance to food products stimulated research on the pathogenesis of the disease and the search for mechanisms to prevent food allergies in children.

The goal of the planned study is to: determine the values of regulatory cytokines TGF β 1 and interleukin 10 in gastrointestinal forms of food allergies in children.

Keywords: food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome, regulatory cytokines, TGF- β 1, Il-10, Ig E.

Materials and methods of research. There were 109 patients aged from 3 months to 3 years under observation. Of the examined patients, 72 were diagnosed with food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome (with FPIES) and 37 with allergic enteropathies (AE). To establish the diagnosis, clinical anamnestic, paraclinical (general blood test, coprology, feces for latent bleeding, total protein), and immunological (Ig E general, Ig E specific to food antigens by ELISA, determination of the lymphokine producing ability of T-lymphocytes to allergens) studies were used.

The results of the study. Of 72 FPIES patients, 46 (63,9%) had elevated Ig E values ($128,3 \pm 30,0$), among patients with AE there were 20 (54,1%), and the average values were $67,1 \pm 19,1$ Cow's milk proteins (100%) were the leading cause of

allergy development in the observed children, monovalent allergy was more often observed in patients with elevated Ig E values. In the subgroup of FPIES with elevated Ig E values, their number was 47,4 %, and in the subgroup of children with low Ig E values in 35% of cases. The Ige values of specific antibodies to cow's milk proteins were clinically significant and amounted to $1,13 \pm 0.4$ units for FPIES and $0,9 \pm 0,1$ for AE. In case of polyvalent allergy, the causes of food allergy in FPIES were most often beef, eggs, chicken, gluten, soy and citrus fruits were less common. With AE, approximately the same sequence was observed, the values of TGF- β 1 were increased in all groups of patients, higher values of TGF- β 1 were found in patients in the subgroup of patients with high values of Ig E, respectively $42,01 \pm 7,5$ what units and 25.4 ± 6.3 pg/ml, $p < 0.05$, with AE, these values were lower and amounted to 33.7 ± 15.4 in the first subgroup of 30.2 ± 2.8 which units at a norm of 0.43 ± 0.2 pg/ml. The values of IL 10 among patients with FPIES had different values depending on the values of Ig E, so in the subgroup of children with FPIES with elevated values of Ig E, they amounted to 42.8 ± 14.2 pg/ml, and with low values of Ig E- 25.4 ± 6.3 pg/ml, with values in the control group 10.7 ± 2.3 pg/ml. Among patients with AE, these figures were 52.4 ± 16.6 pg/ml (with elevated Ig E values) and 15 ± 3.5 pg/ml (with normal Ig E values). The level of tumor necrosis factor α was significantly increased in both forms of the disease, a comparison between them showed that the highest values were noted in the group of patients with the most severe form of the disease: FPIES associated with high values of Ige: 11.2pg/ml, while the indicators of healthy children were 4.3 ± 0.7 pg/ml. ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion. The data obtained strongly suggests that cytokines of the TGF- β and IL-10 groups in gastrointestinal forms of food allergies perform the functions of regulators of inflammatory reactions. The regularities of the influence of the levels of transforming growth factor β 1, interleukin 10 on the activation of the process in gastrointestinal forms of food allergy, more pronounced in the association of the underlying disease with elevated values of Ig E.

Mortality predictions in elderly patients with acute heart failure in the intensive care unit

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Key words: heart failure, frailty, elderly, senile age, mortality.

Introduction. A number of factors of unfavorable outcome in the acute of chronic heart failure (AHF) have been identified according to research data. The role of geriatric syndromes as predictors of mortality in elderly patients with AHF has not been sufficiently studied. Assessment of the syndrome of senile asthenia as a marker of mortality in patients with AHF in the intensive care unit (ICU) is relevant.

Objective: to evaluate and identify the most significant predictors of mortality and prolonged ICU stay in patients with AHF.

Materials and methods: 107 patients aged 46-95 years with AHF functional class III-IV were included. 4 groups were formed: 1st - 29 people (53.9 ± 4.5 years), middle age (46-60 years); 2nd - 31 people (68.3 ± 5.0 years) elderly (61-74 years); 3rd - 40 people (81.5 ± 4.1 years) old age (75-89 years). 4th - 7 people (92.4 ± 1.4 years) of the age of centenarians (> 90 years). The patients underwent: examination, echocardiography. Geriatric syndromes were assessed using a comprehensive geriatric assessment (CGE) using the Specialized Geriatric Examination program.

Results. The longest duration in ICU was in the old age group- 5.13 ± 1.9 days. Mortality in the ICU on the 1st day was 1.07%, over the whole period - 14%. The most significant independent predictors of mortality in ICU (OR [95% CI]) were terminal stage of CHF ($52.5 [4.62; 1419.34]$, $p < 0.01$), severe frailty with terminal ($32.0 [5.59; 608.84]$, $p < 0.01$), IV functional class NYHA ($10.6 [2.72; 70.31]$, $p < 0.01$). The most significant independent predictors of long-term stay in ICU (OR

[95% CI]) were terminal stage of CHF (3.6 [2.57; 5.38], $p < 0.01$), terminal frailty (2.9 [1, 85; 4.59], $p < 0.01$), severe frailty (2.6 [1.72; 3.97], $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion. Terminal and severe senile asthenia are independent predictors of a 32-fold increase in mortality and an almost 2.9-fold increase in the duration of stay in ICU of elderly and senile patients.

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE

Processes of physical training of young handball players

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Annotation: This article deals with the activity of movement of handball players in the game and the implementation of technical and tactical processes in the game, as well as the physical qualities of handball players.

Keywords: Handball, game, group, ball, action, physical, technique, tactics, preparation, skill, skill.

Handball is the most popular sport in the world. Today, in the educational institutions of our republic, the sport of handball is included in the curriculum as a science and a means of health. Achieving a high result in these situations related to sharp confrontations requires handball players to show the ability of stable movement along with the qualities of quickness, strength, agility, and endurance.

It has been scientifically proven that accurate, fast and effective performance of technical skills, implementation of tactical combinations to the goal appropriate to the situation is closely related to the physical qualities of each type of sports game. In the studies, it was recommended to group and use many sets of exercises designed to develop physical qualities suitable for certain sports (football, volleyball, handball). In particular, group 1 exercises are performed within the rules of the game. Group 2 - in a situation outside the scope of the rules of the game, group 3 exercises do not end with the final shot or ball throw (handball, basketball) (players only pass the ball to each other). Group 4 - each participant individually performs exercises that shape their skills.

The basis of the game of handball is natural movements that help the players to develop harmoniously in all aspects, such as running, jumping, passing the ball, running, throwing. Loads have a positive effect on the development of all functional systems in the body. Under the influence of training, as well as in competitions, mental activity of participants improves, qualities such as speed, imagination, creative thinking and initiative develop. Handball can be a good tool for general

fitness. Handball is a necessary sport for a student of any specialty due to the development of physical qualities, at the same time, willpower, and tactical thinking by changing the direction, different types of running, jumping, and moving at maximum speed. is among the games.

Reminding of the importance of the result of the game and the need to win does not always give good results. Every athlete must have highly developed willpower. Courage, determination, simplicity and perseverance, initiative, discipline is the main willpower. These feelings are nurtured during training.

Preparation for the performance of specified tasks is the basis of the handball player's body capabilities and physical training. The level of such opportunities is clearly reflected in the activity of their supporting muscle system. For training-induced changes to be sustained, a player must be able to perform a specific task over a long period of time.

In the game of handball, methods are performed with and without the ball. Handball technique is a set of different special methods used in the game to achieve the goal. Handball technique is divided into field player technique and goalkeeper technique. Management techniques are divided into sections. Subsections consist of specific techniques performed in different ways - styles and methods of movement techniques. Outfield players and goalkeepers are made of them. The main mechanism of movement in methods and types is common, and differs only in details. The conditions for performing different methods make handball technique even more diverse. Handball technique can be divided into two major parts: "attack" and "defense technique". Attack techniques are divided into "movement" and "possession of the ball" methods, and defense techniques are divided into "movement" and "possession against the ball" methods. Each component contains game activities, which in turn are implemented in several ways. 1) the number of hand and foot movements when performing the technique (one or two); 2) the movement of the hand with the ball in relation to the position of the shoulder (up, side, bottom); 3) the movement of the ball transfer methods (swing, kick).

Acting as an attacker and a defender on the field and the method of deceptive actions are the basis of the game technique. The initial state - determines standing, preparation and movement. Standing high and low are different, the situation dictates which position to stand. In modern handball, standing in a high position (legs slightly bent), shoulder-width apart, body slightly bent forward, and arms are held in a bent position. The player who moves quickly and efficiently on the field will benefit the most.

It is a very important and complex part of training in the process of improving physical qualities. In addition to physical and technical preparation, the ability to use one's own abilities correctly and skillfully is of great importance in winning over the opponent's team. To improve the tactical skills of handball players, repetition of mastered and learned exercises many times is the main method (method) of education and training in tactics.

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